

**Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe
Phase 3**

**Strategy and Requirements for FDO-Standard in
Simulation-based Climate Science
Milestone M3.1**

ESiWACE3 Milestone M3.1

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Introduction

Climate science relies heavily on the effective management, sharing, and analysis of massive and diverse datasets. As the digital landscape evolves, there is a growing need to establish a framework that ensures FAIRness (Wilkinson et al. 2016) in handling digital objects related to climate research. Especially, *machine-to-machine* (M2M) actionability of digital objects will be a crucial step towards future *artificial-intelligence* (AI) assisted workflows. According to the vision of the FDO forum “the global integrated data space will be populated by standardized, autonomous and persistent entities, which contain the information needed about different kinds of digital objects, to enable both humans and machines to *Find, Access, Interoperate, and Reuse* (FAIR) these digital objects in highly efficient and cost-effective ways”¹. *FAIR Digital Objects* (FDOs) are encapsulations of data and their metadata made findable and accessible via *Persistent Identifiers* (PIDs) in a way that data and their context will remain a complete unit as the FDO travels through cyberspace and time (De Smedt et al., 2020). They represent a paradigm shift in data management, emphasizing principles of FAIRness, cross-disciplinary research and M2M actionability. The FDO concept can be applied to various digital objects, including data, documents and software within different research disciplines and industry areas. A strong abstraction hides the technological details and facilitates data usage for researchers of different science backgrounds. Through standardization, FDO operations allow M2M actionable services. This and the easy reusability of FDOs are key factors for an advancement in data science. FDOs can be pictured as a sphere (fig. 1) with various layers. The center shows the bit sequence of the digital object, surrounded by the object's metadata. The outer shell consists of the object's operations and the PID.

Figure 1: Layers of encapsulation in an FDO. Taken from (De Smedt et al., 2020)

¹ <https://fairdo.org/1316-2/> FAIR Digital Objects Forum. Retrieved November 8, 2023

FDOs can provide significant benefits to the climate science community in various ways:

Data Management: Climate science involves the collection and analysis of vast amounts of data from various sources such as satellites, weather stations, and climate models. FDOs can help manage this data through enhancements of PIDs of digital objects like model datasets, and publications. These enhancements could include standardized information on storage location, access conditions and/or licenses. This ensures that data remains accessible and identifiable over time, even as storage locations and metadata evolve.

Data Sharing and Collaboration: FDOs enable seamless data exchange between different research institutions, projects, and stakeholders. Climate scientists can easily share and collaborate on datasets, models, and research findings by referencing FDOs. Moreover, M2M of FDOs promotes interdisciplinary collaboration and accelerates AI assisted workflows. This is of especial importance as reuse scenarios of climate model simulation output are becoming more and more diverse, e.g. to address the multitude of aspects related to climate change adaptation at the level of individual stakeholders. Thereby, applying FDOs to upcoming, exascale climate model simulation output makes the information content of those simulations easily accessible to a broad reuse community.

Data Discoverability: FDOs enhance the discoverability of climate data and research outputs. They help researchers to search for and access specific datasets, models, or publications, making it easier to locate relevant information in the vast climate science landscape.

Workflow Reproducibility: FDOs promote reproducibility in climate science through enrichment by provenance and access rights for digital objects. This transparency helps researchers understand the context of data and research findings, supporting reproducibility and the verification of scientific results.

Interoperability: Processing of climate science datasets provided in diverse data formats involves the usage of a plethora of software tools and platforms. FDOs facilitate interoperability across file formats and analysis platforms by providing a standardized way to reference and exchange digital objects, ensuring that data and models can be used across different systems and applications.

Data Citation: FDOs provide standardized data citation principles, thereby automatically giving credit to data providers and creators. This encourages data sharing and supports researchers who invest time and resources in generating valuable climate datasets.

Policy and Decision-Making: Climate science research informs policies and decisions related to climate change mitigation and adaptation. FDOs help ensure that the underlying data and research findings are well-documented, transparent, and accessible, which is crucial for evidence-based decision-making.

In summary, FDOs offer a standardized and persistent framework for managing, sharing, and preserving digital objects in climate science. They support collaboration, transparency, and

reproducibility, ultimately contributing to more effective climate research and informed decision-making in the face of climate change.

In the following we examine the requirements for FDOs within simulation-based climate data and present a strategy for implementing the FDO concept in the community.

Methodology

The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management (Wilkinson et al., 2016) will be the basis for the formulation of requirements and a strategy towards FDO compliant digital objects in simulation-based climate science. The climate science community already has come a long way in adapting the FAIR principles by applying community-wide accepted (meta)data standards and providing infrastructure solutions for global accessibility of datasets (Peters-von Gehlen et al. 2022). In the work presented here, we focus on the digital objects with the CMIP6 database (Eyring et al.; 2016, Petrie et al. 2021), which already have a high level of standardization and comply with the majority of the FAIR data principles. We use these data to establish a baseline representing the current state of FAIRness of climate simulation output. Note that we only take those CMIP6 data into consideration which are made available directly via the Earth System Grid Federation (ESGF)². Thus, we do not consider CMIP6 data made available by other providers, e.g. the Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S)³ platform or the World Data Center for Climate (WDCC)⁴. This is because the PIDs initially assigned to the CMIP6 data point to ESGF data nodes and therefore represent the baseline of the M2M actionability of CMIP6 data.

We establish the baseline FAIRness of published CMIP6 data by analyzing the compliance of the digital objects within the CMIP6 database with each dimension of the FAIR principles (F, A, I and R). Specifically, we focus on aspects of M2M and cross-domain actionability. If necessary, we will formulate a recommendation for improvements to define the FDO strategy in-line with the ESiWACE3 project goals. The focus of this work so far is the findability and accessibility of digital objects, because these are essential for enabling (meta)data reuse. Therefore, this document provides targeted conclusions and recommendations specifically on data findability and accessibility.

Findability

- **F1. (Meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier**
 - Yes, all digital objects of the CMIP6 database within the ESGF have a PID handle on various aggregation levels. Both individual files (data file PID information, see fig. 5) and file collections (dataset PID information, see fig. 4) have a PID handle.

² <https://esgf-data.dkrz.de/projects/esgf-dkrz/>

³ <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/projections-cmip6>

⁴ https://www.wdc-climate.de/ui/q?query=*&page=0&hierarchy_steps_ss=CMIP6

- **F2. Data are described with rich metadata**
 - The metadata in the PID handles contain very basic information, such as the dataset id, the filesize, checksum, data access links with the location of the file, and links to related files. Comprehensive information about the file content, such as variable names and grid information, are not present in the PID handle metadata.
- **F3. Metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data they describe?**
 - Yes, the metadata contains a clear reference to the file name of the data they describe.
- **F4. (Meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource**
 - CMIP6 data can be searched using the ESGF online GUI⁵ or using the API⁶.

Conclusion & Recommendations on Findability

Currently, there is already a high level of standardization within the climate science community and particularly within CMIP6. The most important aspects are: (1) Standardized file formats that follow NetCDF Climate and Forecast (CF) Metadata Conventions (Hassell et al., 2017) to ensure consistency between climate models. (2) Standardized experiments that participating modeling groups should simulate. These experiments cover a range of scenarios, including historical simulations and idealized future scenarios. (3) Specified standardized grids and coordinates for representing spatial and temporal dimensions in climate model output. This includes guidelines for representing latitude, longitude, time, and vertical planes to improve interoperability and facilitate comparisons between models. (4) Standardized naming conventions for climate model output variables. This ensures that model output variables representing specific climate-relevant parameters are named consistently in different models.

However, it takes specific domain-knowledge to pinpoint the desired dataset from the available published data because there is a lack of unique mapping between the model variable names (e.g. "tas") and their meaningful descriptive names (e.g. "temperature at surface" in this case). This prevents researchers from other disciplines from finding the necessary data for their specific use case or research question. Furthermore, this makes the automatic search for data more difficult. In order to increase the findability of climate model data, there needs to be a unique mapping between model variable names and their meaningful long names.

Additionally, organizing data into intake catalogs⁷ can make finding data easier. Intake is a data loading Python package, which is designed to simplify the process of discovering, loading, and working with datasets in data science and analysis workflows. Intake catalogs serve as organized collections or inventories of datasets, providing a convenient way to manage and access data sources within a project, organization, or research environment. Intake catalogs contain descriptions and metadata for each dataset, including information about variables, data types, units, and any other relevant details. This metadata helps users understand the content and dramatically increases the findability of the desired dataset.

⁵ GUI search call: <https://esgf-data.dkrz.de/search/cmip6-dkrz/>

⁶ API search call:

<https://esgf-data.dkrz.de/esg-search/search?project=CMIP6&format=application%2Fsolr%2Bjson>

⁷ <https://github.com/intake/intake-esm>

Accessibility

- **A1. (Meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol**
 - Data can already be accessed fully automatically, which is shown in the workflow below. This is achieved by resolving the PID handle via the handle server API⁸ and downloading the data via the ESGF⁹.
- **A1.1 The protocol is open, free, and universally implementable**
 - Yes, the HTTP transfer protocol and the Python programming language are free, and universally implementable.
- **A1.2 The protocol allows for an authentication and authorisation procedure, where necessary**
 - This does not apply to the CMIP6 climate data within the ESGF, since they are openly available.
- **A2. Metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available**
 - This has not been tested, as the CMIP6 data is fully available.

The following section describes how to access a dataset with a given PID handle in an automated way. In this way, we will test if the CMIP6 PID handle system fulfills the machine accessibility requirements of a FDO. We will access and visualize a dataset by using the information, which are provided in the PID handle metadata.

Workflow for automated data access:

1. Select an arbitrary dataset PID handle within the CMIP6 catalog¹⁰ (fig. 2).
2. Resolve the dataset PID handle via the handle server API (fig.3).
3. Retrieve the PID handle metadata of the dataset (fig. 4).
4. On this aggregation level the dataset PID handle contains various data file PID handles. Select the desired data file PID handle and retrieve the metadata of the first data file (fig. 5) again via the handle server API.
5. The metadata of the data file PID contains the storage location of the data file and allows access to the file.
6. The PID handle itself only contains very basic information about the file, such as file name and size, and file location for data access, and links to related files. To get more information for meaningful data analysis, such as variable name, unit, range and time span, the file must be opened, for example with the Python Xarray package¹¹.

⁸ <https://hdl.handle.net/api/handles/>

⁹ <https://esgf-data.dkrz.de/projects/esgf-dkrz/>

¹⁰ <https://esgf-node.llnl.gov/projects/cmip6/>

¹¹ <https://docs.xarray.dev/>

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WCRP CMIP6

World Climate Research Programme

You are at the [ESGF@DOE/LNL node](#) **Technical Support**

Home **Contact Us** **Data Nodes Status**

MIP Era **Activity** **Product**

Source ID MPI-ESM1-2-LR (1) **Institution ID** MPI-M (1) **Source Type** **Nominal Resolution**

Experiment ID historical (1) **Sub-Experiment** **Variant Label** r10i1p1f1 (1) **Grid Label**

Table ID day (1) **Frequency** **Realm** **Variable** tas (1) **CF Standard Name**

Data Node

WARNING: Not all models include a variant "r1i1p1f1", and across models, identical values of variant_label do not imply identical variants! To learn which forcing datasets were used in each variant, please check modeling group publications and documentation provided through ES-DOC.

CMIP6 project data downloads are unrestricted. Downloads should be performed with the -s option to a wget script without the need to login. When using this method for download, ensure you are not using additional options, eg. -s and -H should never be combined.

For more information about CMIP6 data please consult this guide: <https://pcmdi.llnl.gov/CMIP6/Guide/dataUsers.html>

Please try our updated ESGF web application (named "Metagrid"), now undergoing beta testing. For this test release we are reaching out for help from users in the community to report any issues they encounter with the application. The beta-test web application can be found at the following site: <https://aims2.llnl.gov/metagrid/> Please see the following page for more information including a FAQ: <https://esgf.github.io/esgf-user-support/metagrid.html>

Enter Text: Display results per page [More Search Options](#)

Show All Replicas Show All Versions Search Local Node Only (Including All Replicas)

Search Constraints: tas | day | r10i1p1f1 | MPI-M | MPI-ESM1-2-LR | historical

Total Number of Results: 1
-1-
Please login to add search results to your Data Cart
Expert Users: you may display the search URL and return results as XML or return results as JSON

1. CMIP6.CMIP.MPI-M.MPI-ESM1-2-LR.historical.r10i1p1f1.day.tas.gn
Data Node: esgf3.dkrz.de
Version: 20190710
Total Number of Files (for all variables): 9
Full Dataset Services: [Show Metadata](#) | [List Files](#) | [WGET Script](#) | [LAS](#) | [Show Citation](#) | [PID](#) | [Globus Download](#) | [Further Info](#)

Figure 2: Search result within the ESGF catalog after setting various filters leads to a PID.

Handle.Net®

Resolve a Handle and View the Values

The web form below will enable you to resolve individual handles and view their associated values. It uses a proxy server, which understands both the Handle protocol and HTTP protocol.

If you type a handle into the text box, and that handle has a URL associated with it as one of its values, the proxy server will instruct your browser to display the location of that URL. If you select "Don't Redirect to URLs", the proxy will display the handle record.

The Handle proxy server uses caching to speed handle resolution. If you check "Authoritative Query", the proxy will bypass the cache, go directly to the responsible handle server, and then refresh the cache with the data for that handle.

Simply appending a handle to the URL <http://hdl.handle.net>, and giving the string to a browser as a location will also resolve that handle. The proxy also supports a REST API, returning handle records in JSON format. [Further documentation is available here.](#)

Handle:

Authoritative Query
 Don't Redirect to URLs
 Don't Follow Aliases

[Handle Proxy Server Documentation](#)
[Handle.net Web Site](#)

Contact hdladmin@cnri.reston.va.us with your handle questions and comments.

Figure 3: Handle.Net® is a service to resolve PIDs.

https://handle-esgf.dkrz.de/lp/21.14100/0163da97-35d1-387c-a51b-0d12fc4d3b24

CMIP6 Data Information View

WCRP CMIP6 ESGF

Dataset CMIP6.CMIP.MPI-M.MPI-ESM1-2-LR.historical.r10i1p1f1.day.tas.gn

General Information

Dataset Id	CMIP6.CMIP.MPI-M.MPI-ESM1-2-LR.historical.r10i1p1f1.day.tas.gn
Persistent Identifier	hdl:21.14100/0163da97-35d1-387c-a51b-0d12fc4d3b24
Version	20190710

Data host(s)

- esgf3.dkrz.de (Original)
- esgf-data1.llnl.gov (Replica)
- esgf.ceda.ac.uk (Replica)
- esgf.nci.org.au (Replica)
- esgf-data04.diasjp.net (Replica)

The file is part of the following aggregation(s)

Error: Handle is not accessible doi:10.22033/ESGF/CMIP6.6595

Files belonging to this dataset

tas_day_MPI-ESM1-2-LR_historical_r10i1p1f1_gn_19500101-19691231.nc	hdl:21.14100/c2d50ea5-bca1-40c3-98d6-f59be346427a
tas_day_MPI-ESM1-2-LR_historical_r10i1p1f1_gn_20100101-20141231.nc	hdl:21.14100/cc24787d-209c-45b2-bb70-6955805c3c8
tas_day_MPI-ESM1-2-LR_historical_r10i1p1f1_gn_19100101-19291231.nc	hdl:21.14100/9ecb6707-da42-46f8-8541-289ef3c22242
tas_day_MPI-ESM1-2-LR_historical_r10i1p1f1_gn_19700101-19891231.nc	hdl:21.14100/0718db26-ca1a-418a-9af8-45b3614f2077
tas_day_MPI-ESM1-2-LR_historical_r10i1p1f1_gn_19300101-19491231.nc	hdl:21.14100/d9a886dc-5f59-41da-a7fb-d7ae560d420
tas_day_MPI-ESM1-2-LR_historical_r10i1p1f1_gn_18500101-18691231.nc	hdl:21.14100/5d43d0de-c2e8-47d9-8efa-4fa08a9c6f47
tas_day_MPI-ESM1-2-LR_historical_r10i1p1f1_gn_18700101-18891231.nc	hdl:21.14100/b0881eb-a353-4e7d-b475-aa39e469462f
tas_day_MPI-ESM1-2-LR_historical_r10i1p1f1_gn_19900101-20091231.nc	hdl:21.14100/750483f-1189-4713-9864-cf05031e1ee6
tas_day_MPI-ESM1-2-LR_historical_r10i1p1f1_gn_18900101-19091231.nc	hdl:21.14100/2b7b5bf1-3c20-4e36-a3dc-7fe22c20f626

This PID landing page service is provided by (German Climate Computing Centre).

Figure 4: Human-readable dataset metadata showing the included data files.

https://handle-esgf.dkrz.de/lp/21.14100/c2d50ea5-bca1-40c3-98d6-f59be346427a

CMIP6 Data Information View

WCRP CMIP6 ESGF

File tas_day_MPI-ESM1-2-LR_historical_r10i1p1f1_gn_19500101-19691231.nc

General Information

Dataset Id	tas_day_MPI-ESM1-2-LR_historical_r10i1p1f1_gn_19500101-19691231.nc
Persistent Identifier	hdl:21.14100/c2d50ea5-bca1-40c3-98d6-f59be346427a
Filesize	248767515
Checksum (SHA256)	7b363966535d97462fd4f964731598a2024b35ad11d8b34a720a1a631570c69

Data access

esgf3.dkrz.de http://esgf3.dkrz.de/thredds/fileServer/cmip6/CMIP/MPI-M/MPI-ESM1-2-LR/historical/r10i1p1f1/day/tas/gn/v20190710/tas_day_MPI-ESM1-2-LR_historical_r10i1p1f1_gn_19500101-19691231.nc (Original)

Figure 5: Human-readable file metadata showing the location of the file.

Conclusion & Recommendations on Accessibility

As described above and demonstrated in a Jupyter Notebook¹², the CMIP6 metadata allows for fully automated data access when the PID is known. However, the shown workflow is a custom-made Python-based example and does not portray a standardized solution. Moreover, the PID itself only contains very basic information about the file, such as dataset id, the filesize, checksum, data access links with the location of the file, and links to related files. To obtain

¹² https://gitlab.dkrz.de/data-infrastructure-services/fdo/-/blob/master/automated_data_access.ipynb

further information such as variable name, unit, area and time period covered by the dataset, the file must be opened. This step requires domain knowledge, as the user needs to know how to open a NetCDF file and where to find the relevant information necessary to perform a meaningful analysis.

On a higher aggregation level PID handles are part of *Digital Object Identifiers* (DOIs). These identifiers in CMIP6 contain a wealth of information in a human readable form. However, it is currently not possible to process CMIP6 DOIs automatically because much information is hidden and accessing them requires skills that cannot be assumed by any user, such as manipulating data access links.

The following recommendations can improve the accessibility of digital objects within CMIP6: A.) It is currently computationally expensive to access metadata that goes beyond the PID profile, because extensive metadata is located in the NetCDF file itself. Moving this metadata to a separate file or enriching the existing PID handle can make it easier to access it. B.) It has been shown that data can be accessed automatically solely with the information provided in the PID. To simplify this process, we proposed a feature to capture PIDs directly to the intake-xarray¹³ community. This feature would make data access easier and more attractive to people outside the climate community.

Interoperability

- **I1. (Meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.**
 - The Climate and Forecast (CF) metadata conventions are a key component of CMIP6, providing a standardized language to describe climate model output.
- **I2. (Meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles**
 - While CMIP6 metadata supports many aspects of the FAIR principles, it's important to note that full FAIR compliance involves additional considerations, such as clear and extensive accessible metadata, and specifically machine-readable metadata. Achieving full FAIR compliance may require additional efforts, some of which are mentioned in our recommendations. The Automated FAIR Data Assessment Tool *F-UJI*¹⁴ can be a helpful tool in assessing the FAIRness of a digital object.
- **I3. (Meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data**
 - Yes, the CMIP6 PID handle records contain references to which data aggregation they belong to and which data files they contain.

¹³ <https://github.com/intake/intake-xarray>

¹⁴ <https://www.f-uji.net/>

Reusability

- **R1. (Meta)data are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes**
 - (Meta)data are described. However, mostly in a human readable format and with a basic number of attributes, such as the dataset id, filesize, checksum, data access links with the location of the file and links to related files. The amount and specificity of machine-readable metadata can be improved.
- **R1.1. (Meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license**
 - Yes, CMIP6 (meta)data are released under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0)¹⁵.
- **R1.2. (Meta)data are associated with detailed provenance**
 - The metadata linked within the attributes of the NetCDF file are associated with provenance information. A sporadic provenance record can be found directly under the “history” attribute¹⁶. Additionally, a more comprehensive documentation is available via a link to the *Earth System Documentation* (ES-DOC)¹⁷, stored in the “further_info_url” file attribute.
- **R1.3. (Meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards**
 - Yes, the meta(data) meet the CF metadata conventions.

Overall Conclusion and Recommendations

The meta(data) of the CMIP6 climate model already largely meet the FAIR principles. In order to meet the criteria for FDOs, in particular M2M and cross-disciplinary actionability, certain aspects can be improved.

In particular, the findability of digital objects required for a particular research question in climate science or a related field shows to be challenging. In order to mitigate this issue, we propose certain strategies: (1) Enriching the PID profiles of climate model data in accordance with the FDO concept and taking into account the needs of the climate science community will lead to improved findability of digital objects, especially for machines. (2) Defining a standardized, unique association between climate model variables and their meaningful descriptive names will increase the findability of climate model data, especially for researchers in other disciplines. (3) Furthermore, combining the FDO concept with existing data management solutions, such as the intake catalogs, can lead to improved data handling in line with prevailing community practices.

¹⁵ <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/>

¹⁶ <https://cfconventions.org/Data/cf-conventions/cf-conventions-1.11/cf-conventions.html#attribute-appendix>

¹⁷ <https://search.es-doc.org/>

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The criterion of data accessibility is already largely met and enables a high degree of automation if the PID handle is known. Discussions are currently underway with the intake-xarray community to further simplify data access.

In terms of reusability, proof of provenance of CMIP6 digital objects is sporadic and limited to the file history in the NetCDF file itself. To create proof of provenance, we propose adopting the PROV data model for provenance (Belhajjame et al., 2013).

Eventually, implementing an FDO standard will benefit the climate science community in several ways: The reusability of the data will facilitate the cost-effective use of existing computationally expensive climate model data. Improved data citation practices will promote data sharing, and ultimately, high transparency will increase the reproducibility of research workflows and consolidate scientific results.

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